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An exploratory study of the efficiency of different models for institutional research funding of European universities: linking ETER and Leiden Ranking databases

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Introduction

Since the 80's of last century many countries have introduced a performance based research funding system (PRFS) for the universities (Checchi et al., 2019).

Zacharewicz et al. (2019) classified the PRFSs in 4 categories (models), using:

1. Quantitative metrics-based assessments including bibliometric indicators (PRFS_qa);
2. Peer review assessments either metrics-supported peer review or exclusively peer review (PRFS_pe);
3. A 'limited form' of performance based funding often combining elements from (1) and (2) and also using performance contracts between the government and individual universities (PRFS_li);
4. No performance-based parameters (PRFS_no).

In each of the first three models a mix of weighed criteria is used and in most cases with these criteria only a fraction of the institutional research funding is allocated (Zacharewicz et al., 2019). Moreover in addition to the latter a university's total research funding includes also external (project) funding of different public authorities and revenues from collaborating with firms and valorisation activities.

The analysis of the effects of institutional research funding models should take into account the different components of the (research) funding and its outcome in the broadest sense. Different aggregation levels can be used: countries, universities, faculties, research units and individual researchers.

Although for many decades PRFSs have been studied (Jonkers and Zacharewics, 2015; Luwel, 2021), the results are less than conclusive as discussed in a literature review by de Rijcke et al. (2016) and by Thomas et al. (2020). Not only has the theoretical framework to be further developed, more robust data are needed.

Methodology and data

In this contribution using an input-output model the efficiency of research funding systems are studied with the university as the unit of analysis. The source for the input data is the European Tertiary Education Register (ETER) database¹.

The ETER database provides information on higher education institutions in 32 European countries including for some countries data on funding and (academic) staff. It covers the period 2011-2016.

The availability of reliable longitudinal data on research funding at the level of universities that are comparably across countries is a longstanding problem (Luwel, 2004). The number of academic staff in FTE (ACASTAFF) is less sensitive to some of these methodological difficulties and they are used as input data. Table 1 gives an overview of the countries for which the ETER database contains this information².

Table 1. Classification of countries based on performance based research funding category and each country's number of universities in the sample

Category	Country	# Univs	Category	Country	# Univs
PRFS-li	Austria	12	PRFS-pe	Portugal	6
PRFS-li	Germany	54	PRFS-pe	United Kingdom	58
PRFS-li	Netherlands	13	PRFS-qa	Croatia	1
PRFS-no	Cyprus	1	PRFS-qa	Czech Republic	7
PRFS-no	Hungary	6	PRFS-qa	Finland	10
PRFS-no	Ireland	6	PRFS-qa	Norway	5
PRFS-no	Spain	41	PRFS-qa	Poland	31
PRFS-no	Switzerland	8	PRFS-qa	Sweden	12

Even these data are not always comparable among countries: the composition of the academic staff differs for example in terms of teaching load and the ratio between tenured staff and researchers on short term contracts. As often done in time series analysis, not the annual data but the first difference (further called change) in ACASTAFF is used as the input variable (Stock & Watson, 2020). As far as no structural changes in the countries' higher education system took place in the time interval studied, using the change in the variables eliminates much of the differences between universities and places the focus on changes within the universities.

In the model the universities' output is limited to publications with the 2021 version of the Leiden Ranking database³ (LR) as the data source. The LR contains information on universities that have over a 4 year period on the average at least 200 publications in the core journals indexed by the Web of Science. The limitation to core journals and the exclusion of local journals enhances the international comparability of universities; additional information is available on the LR webpage.

¹ <http://www.eter-project.com>. The data were extracted from the online version in September 2021. On March 23, 2022 a new realise of the ETER database was put online with data for the years 2017, 2018 and 2019.

² Flanders, Belgium is not included because a structural change in the HE system occurred in the period studied (see section 2)

³ <https://www.leidenranking.com>

For the countries in table 1 the universities in the ETER and LR database were manually matched. As for the staff data, the change in the number of publications is used. Publications are fractionally counted (PUB_FRAC) to correct for overestimating the publication and citation count of middle-sized universities compared to larger and smaller (Lin et al., 2013). A two year time lag is applied between the staff data and the publication data (Crespi & Geuna, 2008).

Intuitively efficiency is understood as the relation between input and output. In the model efficiency is measured in terms of change in the variables and not of their value. Following Sandström & Van den Besselaar (2018) the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) is calculated for the change in ACASTAFF (CAGR-ACASTAFF) over the period 2011-2016 and for the change in PUB_FRAC (CAGR-PUB_FRAC) over 2013-2018.

To compare the efficiency of two PRFS categories a linear regression is made over all universities in these categories with CGAR-ACASTAFF as the independent and CGAR-PUB_FRAC as the dependent variable. Efficiency is operationalized as the residual, i.e. the difference between the actual values of CGAR-PUB_FRAC and the fitted values. To compare the categories the two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test (KS-test), a non-parametric test on the residuals of universities in each of the 2 categories is applied. For this test the null hypothesis H_0 is the proposition that the two samples follow the same distribution.

To conclude, for each of the four PRFS categories its effects on the quality of the universities' output is analysed. The proportion of each university's publications covered by the Leiden Ranking that, compared with the other publications in the same field and in the same year, belonging to the top 10% most frequently cited (PP_top_10_FRAC) is taken as a proxy for high quality contributions to knowledge creation. Again the fractional counting scheme is applied. (Tijssen et al., 2002; Waltman et al., 2012; Sandström & van den Besselaar, 2018).

For the universities in each model the average value of PP_top_10_FRAC (mean) and the coefficient of variation (COV), a measure of the dispersion of data around the mean, are calculated for the publication year 2013 and 2018. Under the condition that the two samples are independent and normally distributed and each sample size is large ($n_i > 30$) a two-sample Z-test can be used to compare the mean value at these two years. The null hypothesis H_0 is $\mu_1 = \mu_2$ where μ_i the mean of the sample at publication year i .

For each of the models to determine whether the COV of two publication years differ significantly a two-sample test statistics based on Miller (1991) and Forkman (2009) is calculated. The null hypothesis H_0 is $\sigma_1/\mu_1 = \sigma_2/\mu_2$ where σ_i is the standard deviation and μ_i the mean of sample at publication year i under the condition that the two samples are independent and normally distributed with positive mean.

For the statistical tests, except for the two-sample test for COV, XLSTAT, an Excel data analysis add-on tool is used. For the two-sample test for COV an application was written by one of the authors

Results

Table 2 gives the results of the KS-test on the residuals of the linear regression of the CGAR-PUB_FRAC on the CGAR-ACASTAFF between the pairs of categories. Only for the categories PRFS-qa and PTFS-li at the 1% significance level and PRFS-qa and PRFS-no at 5% can the null hypothesis that both follow the same distribution be rejected and the

alternative accepted. For the other pairs the p-values are much larger than 0.05 and the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

Table 2. KS test on the residuals of the linear regression of CGAR-PUB_FRAC on CGAR_ACASTAFF for the pairs of the institutional funding categories with H0: the two samples follow the same distribution and Ha: the distributions of the two samples are different.

	PRFS_qa	PRFS_pe	PRFS_li	PRFS_no
PRFS_qa		H0 (p=0.570)	Ha (p=0.001)	Ha (p=0.022)
PRFS_pe			H0 (p=0.151)	H0 (p=0.374)
PRFS_li				H0 (p=0.735)

Comparing the samples of the residuals of the universities in the PRFS-qa and the PRFS-no categories learns that the former are more efficient with median values of 1.008 versus -0.935; the former distribution is significantly shifted to the right (Fig. 1). The same difference is found between the PRFS-qa and PRFS-li samples.

Figure 1. Efficiency of the quantitative metrics-based research funding system (PRFS-qa) versus no performance based funding system (PRFS-no): for each university in the two samples the residual value of the linear regression of CGAR-PUB_FRAC on CGAR_ACASTAFF is given.

The same procedure was used to test the residuals of the German universities, with a 'light PRFS' and the British universities with a peer review based PRFS. The null hypothesis has to be rejected in favor of the alternative that the distribution of the 2 samples are different ($p < 0.0001$). Similarly, the null hypothesis is rejected at the 5% confidence level ($p = 0.02$) for the German universities in one and all the Nordic universities in the other sample. In both cases a comparison of the distribution of the residuals shows that the German universities are less efficient.

For each of the four funding models the normality of the distribution of the PP_10_FRAC was tested at the publication year 2013 and 2018 using the Shapiro-Wilk (SW) and the Jarque-Bera (JB) test.

For the universities in the PRFS-no category the H0 hypothesis has to be rejected at the 5% significance level (see table 3a). The tests mentioned in section 2 cannot be applied as they may lead to spurious results. As an alternative the non-parametric two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is used: at the 5% significance level the two samples follow the same distribution.

Table 3a. KS test on the residuals of the linear regression of CGAR-PUB_FRAC on CGAR_ACASTAFF for the pairs of the institutional funding categories with H₀: the two samples follow the same distribution and H_a: the distributions of the two samples are different.

Category	PY 2013		PY 2018	
	SW	JB	SW	JB
PRFS-no	<i>Ha</i> ($p=0.004$)	<i>Ha</i> ($p=0.001$)	<i>Ha</i> ($p<0.0001$)	<i>Ha</i> ($p<0.0001$)
PRFS-li	H ₀ ($p=0.738$)	H ₀ ($p=0.581$)	H ₀ ($p=0.768$)	H ₀ ($p=0.584$)
PRFS-pe	H ₀ ($p=0.461$)	H ₀ ($p=0.268$)	H ₀ ($p=0.542$)	H ₀ ($p=0.765$)
PRFS-qa	<i>Ha</i> ($p=0.004$)	H ₀ ($p=0.114$)	H ₀ ($p=0.104$)	H ₀ ($p=0.408$)

H₀: The variable from which the sample was extracted follows a normal distribution

For the publication year 2013 and 2018 both tests show the universities in the PRFS-li and PRFS-pe categories are normally distributed (5% significance level; table 3a).

For these funding models the null hypothesis H₀ of the two-sample Z-test cannot be rejected. For the PRFS-li model the same conclusion holds for the two-sample test for COV. On the other hand for the PRFS-pe model the reduction of the dispersion by a third is statistically significant (5% significance level).

For the funding model PRFS-qa at the publication year 2013 only the JB test supports the conclusion that the variable from which the sample was extracted follows a normal distribution (table 3a). The SW test is very powerful, but Yap & Sim (2011) shows that for a symmetric long-tailed distribution the JB test is sufficiently rigorous. The skewness (Pearson, 0.232) and the kurtosis (Pearson, -1.233) of the PRFS-qa sample indicate a rather platykurtic distribution – a fairly symmetric shape with longer, thinner tails compared to a normal distribution - satisfying these conditions.

Table 3b. For the categories PRFS-li, PRFS-qa and PRFS-pe the mean and the coefficient of variation (COV) of the sample of the universities' PP_top_10_FRAC at the publication year 2013 and 2018 are compared.

Category	Z-test	test for COV
PRFS-li	H ₀ ($p=0.086$)	H ₀ ($p=0.852$)
PRFS-qa	<i>Ha</i> ($p=0.019$)	<i>Ha</i> ($p=0.024$)
PRFS-pe	H ₀ ($p=0.936$)	<i>Ha</i> ($p=0.004$)
Values of the sample's mean and COV		
Mean		
PY	2013	2018
PRFS-qa	6.867	8.111
COV		
PY	2013	2018
PRFS-qa	0.458	0.326
PRFS-pe	0.263	0.177

Z-test: H₀: The difference between the means is equal to 0.

Test for COV: H₀: The difference between the 2 COV values is equal to 0.

As the computed p-value is greater than the significance level $\alpha=0.05$, one cannot reject the null hypothesis H₀.

For the universities with a funding model based on quantitative indicators, at the 5% significance level both the mean and the dispersion around the mean of the sample of PP_top_10_FRAC differ significantly between the publication year 2014 and 2018: the average percentage of highly cited papers increased by 1.25% and the dispersion reduced by a

quarter (table 3b). This conclusion was corroborated by two-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test showing that at the 5% significance level the null hypothesis H_0 (the two samples follow the same distribution) should be rejected.

Tentative conclusions and ongoing work

This exploratory study illustrates the potential of linking input and output data with the university as the aggregation level to explore effects of funding models.

A first tentative conclusion is the greater efficiency of the universities in countries using a metric-based funding system compared with those without or with a limited performance based funding model; statistically there is no difference between the peer review and the metrics-based model. Using the proportion of highly cited papers as an indicator, an increase in the quality of the publication output of universities with metrics-based and to a lesser extent peer review based funding is observed. For the other two models no such effect was detected.

However caution is needed: only WoS publications are taken into account and due to limitations in the available ETER data a rather small time interval is used. As recently a new release of the ETER database became available, the analysis presented in this paper will be updated using somewhat longer time series.

More generally, internationally comparable input and output data covering not only publications but the broad range of academic work should be collected to gain insight into the effects of different funding models at the university level but also at lower aggregation levels. These studies could provide background material for more qualitative work on this important aspect of a country's science policy, stimulate experts to better articulate their opinion on different funding models and provide incentives to further develop existing or devise new, more efficient funding models for universities.

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